

Studies in the Thiosemicarbazone Series.

By

PRAFULLA KUMAR BOSE AND DHIRENDRANATH RAY CHAUDHURY.

The hydrazones of $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated aldehydes and ketones, as a rule, undergo pyrazoline conversion either spontaneously or when their solutions in suitable solvents are heated for sometime. Thus the phenylhydrazones of acetaldehyde and mesityl oxide change into phenyl pyrazoline and trimethyl phenyl pyrazoline respectively (Fischer and Knoevenagel, *Annalen*, 1887, 239, 194; *J. pr. Chem.*, 1894, (2), 50, 531; cf. Kishner, *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 45, 987, 957). Benzal-acetophenone phenylhydrazone is transformed into 1:3:5-triphenyl-pyrazoline in warm alcoholic solution (Knorr and Laubmann, *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 1205). Similarly cinnamylidene phenylhydrazone, in hot glacial acetic acid solution, is converted into 1:5-diphenyl pyrazoline (Auwers and Muller, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 2697), although Bauer and Dieterle (*Ber.*, 1911, 44, 2697) found that the reaction of Auwers is not a general one. The change takes place by the migration of the secondary hydrogen atom to the unsaturated part, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}$ of the ketone or aldehyde, thus:—

that is, the open-chain system $-\text{CH}=\text{CH} \cdot \text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{NH}-$ is potentially capable of ring closure.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to examine whether the thiosemicarbazones of unsaturated aldehydes and ketones, which contain the necessary reactive groupings, would similarly undergo pyrazoline conversion, thus:

For this purpose cinnamylidene thiosemicarbazone was heated in glacial acetic acid solution for a few hours but the expected transformation did not occur. Assuming that the substituents of the thiosemicarbazides in position 4, as well as those in the unsaturated aldehyde might have some favourable influence on the above course of reaction, several 4-substituted thiosemicarbazides have been condensed with cinnamic aldehyde and benzalacetone in alcoholic or glacial acetic acid solution. Each of the thiosemicarbazones thus obtained was heated in glacial acetic acid with a view to obtain the expected pyrazoline derivative. But the intramolecular transformation was not observed to take place.

The inability of the imino hydrogen atom to saturate the ethylenic double bond may be attributed to the constitution (III) depicted below, where the hydrogen atom, having migrated over to the S-atom, is no longer available for the pyrazoline transformation (*cf.* Wilson and Burns, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 870; also Bose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 98). In fact the thiosemicarbazones possess acidic properties, and dissolve in cold caustic alkalis thus supporting the above supposition.

The thiosemicarbazones are crystalline substances most of which are pale yellow in colour. When heated with caustic soda, they first dissolve and then decompose liberating the original aldehyde or ketone. Freshly prepared yellow mercuric oxide is coloured black in a minute when an alcoholic solution of the thiosemicarbazone is warmed with it on the water-bath. They produce yellow crystalline precipitates with mercuric chloride in alcoholic solution.

Cinnamylidene benzyl dithiocarbazinate and the product from benzal acetone and benzyl dithiocarbazinate behave similarly. They, however, dissolve in cold alkalis with great difficulty and unlike the thiosemicarbazones are not easily desulphurised by freshly precipitated mercuric oxide. On boiling with alkali for sometime, they decompose, the smell of original aldehyde or ketone being perceptible at the same time.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A General Method for the Preparation of Thiosemicarbazones in Glacial Acetic Acid.

Molecular proportions of cinnamic aldehyde or benzal acetone and thiosemicarbazides are heated in glacial acetic acid solution over a flame. The time required for the preparation of cinnamic aldehyde thiosemicarbazones is about 15 minutes, whereas in the case of the ketone about half an hour is found to be necessary. The condensation products crystallise out on concentrating the solution, and can be purified by recrystallisation from suitable solvents.

Cinnamylidene-4-methylthiosemicarbazone crystallises from benzene by the addition of ligroin in yellow needles melting at 170°. It is fairly soluble in benzene, carbon disulphide, pyridine, acetone and acetic acid but insoluble in ligroin. (Found: S, 14.60. $C_{11}H_{11}N_2S$ requires S, 14.60 per cent.).

Cinnamylidene-4-ethylthiosemicarbazone was crystallised from benzene by the addition of ligroin, in pale yellow needles. It melts at 166-167°. It is soluble in all common solvents except ligroin. (Found: S, 13.59. $C_{12}H_{13}N_2S$ requires S, 13.7 per cent.).

Cinnamylidene-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone has been described (Pulvermacher, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 617) as having a melting point 175-176°, but our product, when crystallised from pyridine, melted at 182-183°. (Found: N, 15.01. $C_{16}H_{15}N_2S$ requires N, 14.95 per cent.).

Cinnamylidene-4-p-tolylthiosemicarbazone crystallises from alcohol in pale yellow crystals which melt at 194°. It is moderately soluble in all solvents. (Found: N, 14.24. $C_{17}H_{17}N_2S$ requires N, 14.50 per cent.).

Cinnamylidene-4-m-tolylthiosemicarbazone comes out from alcohol in almost colourless crystals, m.p. 146°. It is highly soluble in pyridine and acetone but moderately in alcohol and acetic acid. (Found: N, 14.4. $C_{17}H_{17}N_2S$ requires N, 14.20 per cent.).

Cinnamylidene-4-β-naphthylthiosemicarbazone crystallises from a mixture of alcohol and pyridine in almost colourless needles, m.p. 218° with decomposition. It is highly soluble in pyridine, moderately in alcohol and sparingly in benzene, chloroform or glacial acetic acid. (Found: S, 9.22. $C_{20}H_{17}N_2S$ requires S, 9.6 per cent.).

Benzalacetone-thiosemicarbazone was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in pale yellow needles melting at 147-148°. It is fairly

soluble in benzene, chloroform, glacial acetic acid, alcohol, acetone and pyridine. (Found: N, 19.05. $C_{11}H_{13}H_3S$ requires N, 19.18 per cent.)-

Benzalacetone-4-methylthiosemicarbazone is obtained as yellow needles from dilute alcohol. It melts at 149°. It is freely soluble in benzene, chloroform, pyridine, glacial acetic acid and alcohol but insoluble in ligroin. (Found: S, 13.46. $C_{11}H_{13}N_3S$ requires S, 13.73 per cent.).

Benzalacetone-4-a-naphthylthiosemicarbazone comes out from dilute alcohol in yellow crystals which melt at 169°. It is easily soluble in benzene, chloroform, carbon disulphide and pyridine but moderately in alcohol and glacial acetic acid. (Found: N, 12.23. $C_{21}H_{19}N_3S$ requires N, 12.17 per cent.).

A General Method for the Preparation of Thiosemicarbazones in Alcohol.

Condensations could also be successfully effected in alcoholic solution. About two hours' time was necessary to have complete reaction. The following thiosemicarbazones were prepared using alcohol.

Cinnamylidene-thiosemicarbazone crystallises out in pale yellow needles (m.p. 134-135°) from glacial acetic acid. (Found: S, 15.2. $C_{10}H_{11}N_3S$ requires S, 15.6 per cent.).

Cinnamylidene-4-o-tolylthiosemicarbazone comes out as colourless crystals from alcohol. It melts at 207°. It is moderately soluble in alcohol, pyridine, chloroform and benzene. (Found: N, 14.3. $C_{17}H_{17}N_3S$ requires N, 14.2 per cent.).

Benzalacetone-4-o-tolylthiosemicarbazone crystallises from alcohol in yellow needles melting at 185°. It is highly soluble in benzene, chloroform, carbon disulphide and glacial acetic acid but moderately in alcohol. (Found: N, 13.65. $C_{18}H_{19}N_3S$ requires N, 13.59 per cent.).

Benzalacetone-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone.

Molecular proportions of benzalacetone and 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide were heated in pyridine solution for half an hour. The solution was allowed to cool and concentrated. The separated crystals were freed from the mother-liquor and crystallised from

glacial acetic acid in brown needles melting at 163-164°. (Found: N, 14.55. $C_{17}H_{17}N_2S$ requires N, 14.23 per cent.).

It is fairly soluble in benzene, chloroform, pyridine, alcohol but moderately in glacial acetic acid.

Condensation of Cinnamic Aldehyde with Benzyldithiocarbazine.

Benzyldithiocarbazine (1.9 g.) was dissolved in hot anhydrous alcohol, cinnamic aldehyde (1.3 g.) added and the mixture heated on the water-bath for 10 minutes. On cooling the condensation product separated out. This was freed from the mother-liquor and crystallised from pyridine when pale yellow needles melting at 183° were obtained. (Found: N, 9.2. $C_{17}H_{16}N_2S$, requires N, 8.97 per cent.).

It is moderately soluble in alcohol, pyridine and glacial acetic acid but insoluble in ligroin.

Condensation of Benzalacetone with Benzyldithiocarbazine.

Molecular proportions of benzalacetone and benzyldithiocarbazine in anhydrous alcohol were heated on the water-bath for about two hours. The solution, on concentration, deposited red crystals. These were recrystallised from benzene with the addition of ligroin in colourless crystals which turned red on coming in contact with air. It melts at 130-131°. (Found: N, 8.65. $C_{18}H_{18}N_2S$, requires N, 8.58 per cent.).

The compound is soluble in most organic media but insoluble in ligroin.

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